

CONTINUOUS ASSESSMENT WITH SELF-CHECKING TASKS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the applicability and benefits of self-checking tasks in continuous assessment in an electrical engineering course. The method was implemented in the first-year online graduate course of Advanced Power Electronics. The method uses a two-week cycle, where during the first week a task is accomplished on the topic of that week. The tasks include working with data from

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component datasheets, reading and employing application notes, calculations, and simulations. During the second week, the students self-check their tasks using a rubric provided for them and then turn in a corrected version of the task. To keep the cycle going, during the second week, a new topic is also introduced, and a new task is given. The method was assessed based on a student questionnaire and teacher experiences. The method was new to all students. One of the main findings from the questionnaire was that correcting the original task submission supported student learning more than any other form of teaching on the course. However, there were different interpretations of how this support actually worked. The study also showed that there was significant variation between different types of tasks in how the students assessed the relevance of tasks and their difficulty level. Furthermore, students found that some tasks or their outcomes were more suitable for self-checking than others. This was confirmed by the teacher's insights on the course.

1 INTRODUCTION

The term 'continuous assessment' commonly refers to a practice where students' learning is assessed alongside their entire study process instead of merely at the end of the process. Continuous assessment can take many different forms depending on the nature of assessment tasks, timing of the assessment, formation of the final grade, and many other pedagogical design decisions that the teacher makes. Continuous assessment has been reported to have multiple benefits in various fields of engineering education. Previous studies have found that the use of continuous assessment leads to better grades, higher student satisfaction, a higher passing rate, and improved engagement with overall course activities. These studies were performed in chemical engineering [1], process engineering [2], and civil and mechanical engineering [3]. One of the benefits of continuous assessment compared with the end-of-course exam is that it provides students with information about their learning at the time when they still have a chance to adjust their learning methods, correct some misconceptions, or increase learning. However, the information received by the students relies rather heavily on the nature of the assessment tasks and the resources of the instructor for giving feedback.

Self-checking tasks have gained attention and popularity in engineering education in the past few years. Tasks of this kind have also been called flipped homework [4], self-corrected homework [5], dual-submission-with-reflection homework [6], and a self-evaluation and revision method for homework [7]. Such tasks commonly follow a procedure where the student first submits a solution to a task, then corrects it with the help of materials provided by the instructor, and finally submits the corrected version usually also containing reflection of the corrected mistakes and improved learning. Depending on the method, the instructor grades either both submissions or only the corrected version.

The method has been shown to make students take more ownership of their learning and thus also devote more time to solving the tasks [4], [5]. Students also have less stress about the mistakes in the first submission, leading to more honest attempts

and less motivation to rely on solution manuals [8]. With instructor-assessed tasks, there is often a risk that students only pay attention to the grade of the task and do not review the feedback, thereby missing the opportunity to learn from their mistakes [7]. Self-correcting tasks, on the other hand, force the student to face their misunderstandings, thus enhancing their metacognitive skills and learning of the content matter [4], [5], [6], [7], [8].

The instructors also benefit from the self-corrected tasks. Despite the concerns expressed about the effects of continuous evaluation on the instructor workload [9], the users of self-corrected tasks have reported that it does not generate more work for the faculty [4] or even reduces the grading load [6], [8]. Nevertheless, the nature of the grading changes from pointing errors to providing feedback on students' conceptions and learning process, making the assessment process more fulfilling for the instructor [8]. The method also enables the instructor to follow the student understanding (and misunderstandings) of the topic without having to interpret the poorly conducted homework, which gives the instructor more emotional energy to invest in in-depth feedback [6] and the possibility to correct the misconceptions early on, thereby facilitating faster comprehension [7].

Self-checking tasks have been shown to be more effective than the traditional homework model [4]. The method is mostly preferred to the old ways of conducting homework by both the students and the instructors [6], [7]. With clear benefits for student learning and more meaningful use of the instructor's time, the approach appears to be a good choice to pair with continuous assessment practices.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE METHOD

2.1 Course setting

The method of self-corrected tasks was implemented on a first-year master's level course of Advanced Power Electronics, which takes place during the spring semester. The course was organized for the first time during the academic year of 2020-2021, and it was implemented fully online. When the course was organized for the first time during the 2021 spring semester, continuously assessed weekly tasks were selected for the course. Continuous assessment has been found to be a versatile method, and it can be used with various types of tasks. For the course under scope, the continuous assessment accounted for 50% of the grade, combined with an assignment at the end of the course covering the other 50%.

The spring semester includes 14 teaching weeks, and for 13 of these, a weekly assessed task was given on the topic of that week. Out of the 13 weekly tasks, 11 were simulation tasks with Matlab Simulink. These tasks may require initial calculations or component dimensioning, and the simulation results are used for further analysis. After the weekly task deadline had passed, correct solutions, with at least one implementation method, were given to the students.

Even though a short report was turned in with the calculations and analysis of the simulation results, grading such tasks by the teacher was found burdensome and

time-consuming due to the nature of the tasks. The initial calculations and further analysis can be browsed through rather fast, but detecting potential errors in a simulation model would usually require running the simulation in order to find the actual errors. Detailed assessment of the contents of the simulation model and trying to interpret the logic within the simulation is time-consuming, especially when the implementation can be done in various ways.

After the first time the course was organized, it was found that the original implementation was not applicable because of the increased workload for the teacher, and thus, the methodology had to be improved. Regardless of the extensive benefits of continuous assessment, previous studies have also found that the method leads to a significant increase in the workload of the instructors [9].

2.2 Improved method

When the course was organized for the second time in 2022, the approach to overcome the issue of increased workload was to involve the students in the assessment process. A computer-aided assessment process or adaptive homework has been found to decrease the workload of the teacher during the assessment, but may not enhance deeper learning [6]. Moreover, using such tools is not applicable with simulation tasks. Self-checking homework has been proposed previously with positive results [4], [5], [6]. The primary benefits that have been found with the method of self-checking homework are enhanced learning and self-reflecting skills.

Similar to the previous academic year, the weekly topic was accompanied with a task with a deadline by the end of the week. After the deadline for the weekly task, in the second part of the cycle (which overlaps with the topic of the next week), a grading rubric is given to the students. The rubric gives at least one implementation method for the task, and for the majority of the topics, a demonstration video is given to complement the instructions on the grading rubric. The students are instructed to turn in the grade and the corrected task, and the deadline is at the end of the second week. The two exceptions to the cycle used for the method are weeks one (W1) and 14 (W14). For W1, the task was a multiple-choice quiz with automated correction online, and for W14 there was no task, because of a visiting lecture from industry.

The grading of the tasks is split between the initial task and turning-in of the self-corrected task, similar to [6], where the self-assessment accounted for 30% of the grade. With the improved method, all the tasks are graded in the same way. The task that is turned in by the students during the original teaching week is assessed by themselves with a maximum of 8 points during the following week. All the weekly tasks have very different contents, regardless of the emphasis on simulations. For example, the grading is on dimensioning of components, designing circuit topologies, control logic, and analyzing the simulation results. Each week, the students are instructed to turn in a short report with answers to specific questions regarding the results. The corrected task, with the initial calculations file, simulation model, and the short report, are turned in by the end of the second week of the cycle. After the

deadline, the corrected task is assessed by the teacher with a maximum of 2 points, leading to 10 points at the maximum per week.

The improved method was built on the tasks that were used during the previous academic year. The tasks were revised slightly based on the student feedback from the past year, but on a larger scale in order to fit the rubric and the 8-point grading system. Therefore, the number of questions or subtasks was increased, which also made it more straightforward for the students to implement the task.

2.3 Student questionnaire

The aim of the research was to find if the method was truly applicable with the task-based continuous assessment, especially with the tasks being simulations that are conducted independently. The feasibility of the method was assessed with a student questionnaire at the midpoint of the course. The timing of the questionnaire gives room for adjusting the method for the rest of the course. To motivate the students to submit answers, extra points were given upon a completed questionnaire. Out of the 34 active students at the time of the questionnaire, 33 answered the questions. The teacher gave the students feedback based on the questionnaire, and some key areas were emphasized for the remaining part of the course.

3 RESULTS

The first question in the questionnaire was: “1. *Continuous assessment with self-corrected tasks was a new form of learning for me.*” All of the 33 students answered this statement to be true. When a new teaching method is applied for the whole student body of the course, it will take some adjusting and effort from the students to orient themselves to the new practices.

The second question was: “2. *The teaching methods described below supported my learning. Use an average value over the first weeks of the course.*”² The subquestions and the mean and standard deviation (STD) values of the answers are given in Table 1. The two teaching methods that supported the students’ learning most were the demonstration videos and correcting the original task. However, the differences were not statistically significant (two-way t-test, significance level $p < 0.1$).

Table 1. Mean and standard deviation of the answers to question 2, $n=33$.

		Mean	STD
2.1	Video lectures and their lecture material	3.64	0.80
2.2	Demo videos on simulations	3.85	1.08
2.3	Weekly tasks	3.61	0.92
2.4	Self-assessing the weekly task with the rubric	3.66	0.95
2.5	Correcting the original submission of the task	3.88	0.88

² scale in questions 2.1-2.5: 1=Strongly disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly agree

Correcting the task is the most important part of the cycle of the method, and it was also acknowledged in terms of learning by the students, both in ratings given for question 2, and in open comments for question 3. These results are in line with the results found in [6].

The next question was: “3. Briefly describe your learning process when using self-checking tasks.” Students’ answers confirmed many of the findings from prior research. A couple of students pointed out that without self-checking one would not necessarily go through the mistakes and correct ways of doing things at all, as suggested by [7]:

“You actually look into your task versus if the points just came by the teacher’s evaluation it is possible that you wouldn’t ever look the right answer and come back to the task to do it correctly.”

Also learning from mistakes [8] was mentioned often as a central feature of the learning process:

“There were “Exactly!” moments when fixing the task. These moments will be remembered.”

In this respect, the strength of the method is not only in that the mistakes reveal misunderstandings and unclear issues both to the students and the instructors, but also that the correction round reduces the pressures of getting things absolutely right in the first submission and thus encourages the students to solve the problems themselves instead of consulting solution manuals or other sources of ready-made solutions [8].

Many students emphasized the learning by doing aspect of the method, and some pointed out that seeing alternative ways of solving the problems develops one’s thinking:

“It is interesting to compare your own output and task because there are so many different solutions. This is how you can change your thinking. Next time you can evaluate how to do it better.”

Students also perceived that this method takes up more time than traditional homework, but also linked it to learning more or better, as suggested in [4].

Probably the most common challenge in the learning process was related to situations where the student started to solve the problem very differently from the teacher. In these cases, the self-evaluation and correction were perceived difficult:

“Sometimes I opt for a different method if I am unable to perform in the suggested way, and in such circumstances it becomes difficult to self-grade the tasks.”

This became particularly evident from the answers to question 7, where students were asked to elaborate on the difficulties they met during the course.

In order to find out the perception that the students have on each weekly task, the following question was asked: “4. *Evaluate the relevance of each task.*”³. The follow-up question “5. *Elaborate on how relevant and/or rewarding you found the tasks.*” also provided insight on how the students assessed the relevance of each task. These questions are interesting for the teacher to assess the learning outcomes of the students reflecting on the lectures and the demonstration videos. The mean and STD values of the answers to question 4 are given in Table 2. Clear differences can be seen in the results, yet only the task for W6 stands out with a lower mean value. From the teacher’s perspective, all of the tasks are relevant, but the task for W6 was clearly too difficult for the majority of the students. Based on the answers to question 5, the major issue was that the initial knowledge level and programming skills were insufficient for the completion of the task. As a result, a very thorough task demonstration video was given, but the task must be revised for the following year.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of the answers to question 4, n=33.

	W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W6	W7
Mean	3.76	4.03	4.12	4.15	3.94	3.03	3.72
STD	0.91	0.65	0.76	0.71	0.81	1.42	0.91

The following two questions were used to evaluate how difficult the students found each part of the method: “6. *How difficult did you find the following (on average).*”⁴ and “7. *If you found some of these difficult, please elaborate on.*” The mean and STD values to question 6 are shown in Table 3, and based on the answers, the most difficult part was doing the tasks. The comments in question 7 highlighted that there were difficulties with the new simulation environment, and certain tasks were found especially difficult. The procedures of self-checking and correcting the tasks were found slightly on the easier side, which can be interpreted in favor of the method. In question 7 there were a few comments on uncertainties with the rubric at places where it did not thoroughly specify certain parts of the task results. These rubrics will be revised for the next year.

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation of the answers to question 6, n=33.

		Mean	STD
6.1	Weekly tasks	3.97	0.63
6.2	Self-assessing the weekly task with the rubric	2.82	0.99
6.3	Correcting the original submission of the task	2.88	0.71

³ scale: 1=Strongly irrelevant 2=Irrelevant 3=Neutral 4=Relevant 5=Strongly relevant

⁴ scale: 1=Very easy 2=Easy 3=Neutral 4=Difficult 5=Very difficult

An interesting point relating to the development and importance of metacognitive skills was illustrated in one student's general comments about the course:

"It is not perhaps difficult but it is a bit scary to assign yourself the grade, so it can lead to unnecessary doubting of your own results."

Although reflection skills are often emphasized with respect to situations in which the student needs to evaluate the soundness of their solution, one could argue that also reflection upon confidence in one's solution is a valuable skill in working life and thus something that should be developed during studies. The self-checking method seems to serve also this purpose and promote self-regulated learning [10].

A mismatch with the workload and grading between tasks can be unmotivating, and therefore, the following question was used to get the students' perception: "8. Do you feel that the weekly grading principle of 8 points per task and 2 points for correcting and resubmitting the corrected task is fair." There were three alternatives:

- a) Yes.
- b) No, the original task should be weighted more.
- c) No, the self-checking should be weighted more.

Out of 33 answers, 25 answered 'Yes', which is 75.8%, while the remaining 8 (24.2%) answered that the self-checking should be weighted more. Therefore, the grading can be found to be in line with student efforts, even though if the initial ratio had been 70% and 30%, the result to this question could have gained an even more positive response.

The final question was: "9. The feedback provided by the grading rubric and the video feedback were sufficient to enhance my learning."⁵ The mean value to the question was 3.58 and STD = 0.87. These values still leave room for improvement in the implementation of the method, especially with better rubrics.

4 SUMMARY

The results from the student questionnaire indicate that continuous assessment using self-checking tasks supports well both the learning of the content and the development of metacognitive skills and self-regulated learning. However, the suitability of self-checking depends to some extent on the nature of the primary task.

As for the amount of work effort by the teacher spent on revising the tasks, generating the rubric and the videos took approximately one working day each. This was approximately the same amount of work that was spent on checking the tasks during the previous year. The time spent on checking the short reports and the corrected tasks depends on the week, being nevertheless two hours at the maximum, which was significantly less than during the previous year. As a result, the time invested in modifying the teaching method will be beneficial in the future academic years.

⁵ scale: 1=Strongly disagree 2=Disagree 3=Neutral 4=Agree 5=Strongly agree

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